

CREATIVE APPROACH TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF READING CULTURE OF PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

Aymatova A.

Independent researcher of Tashkent state pedagogical university named after Nizami

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Abstract. *This article discusses about the content of a creative approach to the development of reading culture in future elementary school teachers, the methods, tools, ways used in this process.*

Keywords: *future primary school teacher, reading culture, artistic perception, independent thinking, creative ability.*

It is known that a book in general, a work of art should ensure the moral perfection of people's worldview, socio-political potential. Indeed, such works are being created, and our people, especially our youth, do not get tired of reading them. However, today it is not possible to put such an assessment on all the works. Although some works are created with good intentions, they have a "reverse effect". We are witnessing that various negative manifestations, violence, beatings, attempts to raise the level of "mob mentality" in people, obscenity, promotion of vices are on the rise in some works. Our thinkers-scholars say that the first sign of ignorance is not seeing beauty. Indeed it is. So many news, updates, reforms are happening around us, the way of thinking of our people is changing. It would be very appropriate to convey these positive situations to our people, especially to our youth, through artistically mature works.

In our opinion, finding a hero of our time and creating his image in culture, art, especially fiction is one of the most urgent issues. This is one of the most important issues mentioned in the presidential decree. Some do not "see" the hero of our time. However, it should be emphasized that such heroes are with us, among us, they show courage every day. The fault is that we did not see them. Those who repeated Farhad's bravery on the Angren-Pop railway, showed courage in strengthening the border, increased the productivity of the farming movement based on new technologies, and raised the country's flag high in various world arenas, are they not the heroes of our time?

Our people are waiting for such books. Some of our compatriots say that "although they recommend serious works of art to today's youth, they do not read such books, because times have changed." That is true, times have changed. But our Uzbekism has not changed. At this time, it seems that we sometimes forget to recommend something to improve the reading culture of our young people, to form their spiritual needs. In order to form the spiritual needs of young people, we should recommend meaningful works to them.

In the decree, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev emphasized the need to raise the culture of reading books. So, what do we mean by reading culture? These, in our opinion, include the following: to be able to choose a book and read what is necessary for oneself in order to improve one's professional expertise and artistic-spiritual perfection; learn the skill of working on a book thoroughly and be able to apply it thoroughly; being able to read a book independently; to be able to interpret the main content of the book, to be able to enter its fascinating world; draw vital conclusions from what they read; copying the necessary parts of the book to a side notebook, trying to remember unfamiliar words; to have the ability to read regularly; treat the

book with the same care as your dearest friend; to be able to use the book correctly so as not to make it useless; to acquire the skills to read a book without haste, to think and carefully, to learn how to work with library cards; share the book you have read with your friends, recommend a good book to them and get others to read it; knowing that every good book is the key to the castle of knowledge and ensuring its eternal life.

In our opinion, this order will serve to further stabilize the socio-cultural environment of Uzbekistan, increase the reading level of our youth, and ultimately make the lifestyle of our people more prosperous. At this point, in order to further increase the interest of our young people in reading books, it is appropriate to organize an additional test on writing an essay on the subject of "Uzbek language and literature" during their admission to higher education institutions. The fact is that every year around 550-600 thousand young men and women graduate from vocational colleges and academic lyceums and try to enter higher education institutions. And the essay that is recommended to be written will undoubtedly increase their responsibility to read a work of art.

At the same time, it is necessary to organize the sociological survey specified in the order with utmost responsibility in order to form the reading culture of young people. Such a survey, on the one hand, determines the level of reading culture of young people, on the other hand, it allows to identify the problems that society requires, and to choose topics. Also, we think that it will be of particular importance for experts and industry workers to compile a list of "100 works recommended for young people" and recommend reading rare masterpieces of national and world literature.

Reading enriches the spiritual world of all of us, improves our conversational culture. In some cases, it is necessary to read a book to prevent some of our compatriots from becoming rude and poor due to the "service" of our sacred Uzbek language. However, our Uzbek language is one of the richest languages in the world. A.S. Pushkin used a total of 21,197 words throughout his work, while the language of Shakespeare's works used more than 20,000 words. Spanish scientists reported that 18,000 words were used in Cervantes' work. The number of words used in the works of our great grandfather Alisher Navoi is more than 26,000. (Kadyrov P. Til et al.-Tashkent, 2010, page 127)

It is necessary to read books to preserve our national wealth. In fact, increasing reading culture is the demand of the times and concepts.

On the way to increase the reading culture, the book is, first of all, a school of life, a source of spirituality. It introduces the reader to life, educates him to love life, to understand the essence

of living. Forms a positive attitude to the environment and nature, explains the complexities of human character, develops the ability to discover the colorful aspects of the spiritual image, the feeling of loyalty to the Motherland and its people. By reading fiction, the reader's artistic perception, ability to think independently, reading culture, and sense of responsibility for the fate of the Motherland are cultivated. No matter what type and genre the work of art belongs to, its essence embodies a number of didactic features and aesthetic principles aimed at improving the human personality, developing the ability to think independently, and educating human qualities. "The most important feature of a work of art is that it softens the heart of a person, sharpens his feelings, and educates spiritual perfection."

Since fiction illuminates human life, gives light to human life, shapes and elevates the spiritual world, helps to choose the right path for a bright future, and the book is a great discovery created by mankind, at any age and time, reading books and promoting the culture of reading books has become very important. Especially today, at the initiative of the head of our state, Sh. Mirziyoyev, these issues were considered at the level of state policy, and effective work was started. In particular, on the basis of the strategy of action on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, the great changes being implemented in all sectors and areas, first of all, to improve the social life of the people, to raise their spiritual and educational thinking, focused on creating an equally beautiful and comfortable living environment for everyone. It is of incomparable importance to inculcate noble values and traditions in the life of the society, in particular, to raise the spiritual and intellectual potential of our people, especially the young generation, their thinking and worldview, and to educate a well-rounded person who lives with love and loyalty to the Motherland and its people. Serious importance was given to improving the reading culture. This is clearly reflected in the following comments of the head of our country, Sh. Mirziyoyev: "At the same time, along with mastering the latest achievements in the field of information and communication, we want to increase the interest of young people in reading books, make them friends with books, it will be necessary to pay special attention at increasing the reading level of the population. For this, first of all, it is important that we place the best examples of our national literature and world literature on social networks and pay special attention to their wide promotion." PD-4789 of January 12, 2017 "On the establishment of a commission for the development of the system of printing and distribution of book products, the promotion of book reading and reading culture" is extensive in this regard. The adoption of the resolution PR-3271 dated September 13, 2017, "On the program of comprehensive measures to develop the system of publication and distribution of book products, increase and promote book reading and reading culture" and within its framework the set of tasks also created the ground for great changes in publishing book products in our country, improving the reading culture of the population. In this regard, a solution was found to the serious shortcomings and problems in the field of book printing and distribution, book purchase, and a step was taken to form a book-reading society and spiritual and educational development.

In order to ensure the implementation of this order and decision, all state and non-state organizations and their departments have launched planned and targeted activities based on the program of measures aimed at solving the tasks specified in the decision. In particular, organization of "Young Reader", "Most Active Reader Group", "Most Reader Family" contests across the country and awarding the winning readers with valuable prizes of various levels; the masterpieces of Uzbek people and the world literature will be re-edited and published with better

quality by major publishing houses, the gifting of artistic and aesthetic books, fiction literature to citizens and families in need of social and spiritual support will be the fulfillment of the tasks specified in these laws along with this, the population, especially the young generation, is creating opportunities to improve their reading culture and to raise their spiritual and educational thinking. Also, the Republican Spirituality and Enlightenment Center has organized a number of activities aimed at promoting reading among the population, raising the sense of patriotism in the hearts of the young generation, and increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational activities in the localities. During the events, various book exhibitions were organized and a number of books published by the Republican Center for Spirituality and Enlightenment were presented to the participants of the event and the general public as free and impartial gifts.

On the initiative of the Republican Spirituality and Enlightenment Center, the opening of the "Library of Spirituality" channel on the Telegram mobile messenger in order to promote reading among the general population, including young people, and to spend their free time meaningfully makes it possible for the renewal and improvement of the spiritual life of the society. Every activity in this regard will always be relevant and ongoing.

Formation of reading culture among young people. It is no exaggeration to say that information technology and electronic devices, which are entering the life of societies, have become the basis of life. However, the books containing the knowledge gained by mankind until this time are losing their importance for the society and especially for the young generation. But in our country, especially among young people, the efforts being made to establish the tradition of reading books, pay attention to book reading, and encourage it are noteworthy. Note that it took a million years from man's discovery of fire to the invention of the wheel. The time from the wheel to printing paper was only a few thousand years. A few hundred years later, the telescope was invented. In the following centuries, in a very short period of time, we managed to create rockets from the steam engine to gasoline-powered cars. After that, it only took about twenty years to make a change in our DNA. In our time, scientific innovation is made every month. After a while, today's fastest supercomputer will appear to be a distant computing machine; the most modern surgical methods seem wild, and advanced energy sources give the impression of candles used by our ancestors. It can be seen from this that humanity can update techniques and technologies day by day, but the society cannot be separated from the book, which is a source of knowledge that is dear to it. The development and rapid introduction of new information technologies increases the importance of reading in society. An example of this is the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 13, 2017. But we need to understand one fact - society is always a forward-moving mechanism. That's why today almost no one wants to get familiar with libraries and books. But this does not apply to the stratum of society whose main activity is to study and acquire knowledge. Therefore, today, books and reading places should be modernized. This means that it is time to convert books from paper to electronic, and libraries to electronic books. Therefore, it is appropriate to coordinate actions in the form of a separate system that includes the family and the school at the primary level for the formation of young people. The concepts of reading and reading literacy have changed over the years and have been reflected in the fields of society, economy, culture and technology. Reading is no longer considered to be a skill acquired only in the early stages of education, in childhood.

Today, this ability is defined as a set of knowledge, skills and abilities, methods developed by a person throughout his life on the basis of communication with his peers and the general public in various contexts. There are a number of factors that can affect the formation of reading literacy:

- school factor;
- teacher factor;
- student factor;
- family atmosphere.

In fact, a child is brought up and polished by reading various scientific and artistic books in an educational institution. If students acquire theoretical information from school textbooks, fiction plays an important role in shaping them into perfect human beings. When reading fiction books, students read a text filled with events, places of events, images, consequences, characters, the atmosphere of the work, feelings and ideas and enjoy the language of the text.

In order to understand and appreciate literature, every reader must think about the events, emotions, language, and artistic form of the text. Literature provides an opportunity for young readers to discover situations and emotions that they have not yet experienced. Although the events and actions depicted in the work of art are fictional events, they give the reader an idea of what is happening in real life and allow the reader to experience them in his imagination. The teacher makes students interested in fiction during lessons and classes. In addition, the effective and expected result is achieved when children are interested in reading, instilling a love for books in a family environment, that is, family reading in the family circle. The activities implemented by the government in the formation of the culture of reading among young people, that is, reading activities, allow them to perceive various situations and eliminate them. Especially in the family circle, reading together and analyzing the information brings a number of advantages. Based on the studies, if the following activities are carried out in cooperation with the family and school, it is possible to achieve effective results by increasing the interest of teenagers in books and reading. Along with the formation of reading culture, it is important because it forms aspects such as patriotism, loyalty to values among young people. In addition, there is a need to classify books according to their selection, purposefulness and field relevance. Taking these areas into account, interest in the book and ease of reading would have been created.

REFERENCES

1. Sawyer, R. K. (2011). *Explaining Creativity: The Science of Human Innovation*. Oxford University Press.
2. Craft, A. (2002). *Creativity Across the Primary Curriculum: Framing and Developing Practice*. Routledge Falmer.
3. Kucirkova, N., & Littleton, K. (2017). Digital Storytelling as a Tool for Teaching and Learning in the Digital Age. *TechTrends*, 61(6), 523-532.
4. Papert, S. (1993). *Mindstorms: Children, Computers, and Powerful Ideas*. Basic Books.
5. Serafini, F. (2013). *Reading Workshop 2.0: Supporting Readers in the Digital Age*. Teachers College Press.